

Production of Household Linen From Fabric Waste for Sustainable Living of Homemakers in Cross River State

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Abstract

The study produced household Linen from fabric waste as a means for sustainable living of homemakers in Cross River State. Specifically, the study answers three research questions. Five(5) prototype household linen were developed from fabric waste, and the acceptability test was carried out. The area of the study was Cross River State, the study adopted Research and Development (R&D) design. The population for the study was 1,203 consisting of dressmakers, Home Economics teachers in secondary schools located in the three local government Areas and Home Economics/Clothing and Textile lecturers in Federal and State Universities in Cross River state. The sample size for the study was 120. A structured questionnaire and a 9 point hedonic scale evaluation test were the instruments used for data collection. The instruments were validated by three experts from the Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Crombach Alpha reliability method was used to test the reliability of the instruments and the result yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.89 and 0.78 respectively. The result from the research question and the 9 point hedonic test were both analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The major findings from the study identify; 15 household linen that can be produced from fabric waste these include; Table cover, curtains, throw pillows, bed cover, pillow cases, Wall hanging, TV Cover, Head and Arm Rest, Place mat, Rag Rug, Shoe Hanger, Suit Hanger, House Coat, Chair pad and Glass Case. 5 prototypes of household linen produced are Quitted bed cover, Pillowcases, Table cover, Throw pillow and Curtain. Acceptability level based on aesthetic attributes of household linen produced from the fabric waste, means include 8.37 for bed cover, 7.84 for curtains, pillow case mean 7.95, Table cover 7.84 and Throw pillow 8.16. In conclusion, waste fabrics can be put into use again, therefore waste not lack not, is a key for sustainable living. Recommendations were both for dressmakers and Home Economists to utilize fabric pieces which are considered waste to produce household linen. This requires some form of training which can be delivered by Home Economists.

Key Words: Household, Linen, Fabric waste. Sustainable Living, Homemaker

Introduction

Clothing alongside food and shelter has been one of the primary needs of mankind. Anyakoha and Eluwa, (2015) defined clothing as anything worn on the body to cover, protect or adorn it. The functions of clothing include Protection, adornment, or beautification, to express uniqueness and creativity, decoration, keeping the body warm, modesty among others (Roach & Joanne, 2019). In the context of this study, clothing are pieces of waste fabrics that

could be used for producing different household clothing items, Clothing are made by constructing and assembling fabric pieces together. Ugwu (2018) stated that clothing construction is the skill of making garment to fit a body whatever the person's body shape may be. During clothing construction fabric wastes are generated.

Waste is a material or item that is abandoned and not put into any use. According to Ebikapede (2016) waste is an

unavoidable by-product of most human activity. Bader (2015) explained waste as substances and object discarded as worthless or unwanted, defective or of no further value from a manufacturing or production process. Waste in this study is small pieces of fabrics cut out from the main fabric by dress makers. Fabric is cloth or textile material made from a hair-like unit of raw material called fiber (Igbo, 2013). Onyishi (2013) explained that fabric is made from a variety of materials which come from four main sources: animal (wool, silk,) (plant cotton, flax, jute); mineral (asbestos, glass fibers) and synthetic (nylon, polyester and acrylic).

Fabric wastes produced by dressmakers are heaped in their shops or littered in the surroundings as a waste. The fabric wastes are sometimes burnt because of the challenges of evacuating them and non-utilization in any other meaningful way. The burning of these wastes causes environmental pollution, health hazards. Burning soil degradation and environmental pollution in form of smoke which is detrimental to health. The costs of durable household clothing items are expensive. The high cost of these items makes it unaffordable to a lot of people especially the low-income homemakers

If fabric waste can be utilized for household linen, it would generate additional income for the dressmakers. It would also improve family economy, prevent health hazard, and reduce environmental pollution caused by burning and incineration, and this can bring about sustainability. For a sustainable living, Dashita (2013) pointed out that these fabric wastes can be used to construct useful items such as household line Household line according to Anyakoha and Eluwa (2015) include bed cover, table cover, rag-rug, among others. Household linens are used to cover rough surfaces of objects, they protect objects from scratch, and dust and they add beauty to household environment. Household linen can be produced by using fabric waste gathered from sewing shops, also bearing in mind the aesthetic attributes

of the household linen. According to Shwetank and Rashimi (2020), an aesthetic attribute is the quality element which adds value to the product, such as color, texture, shape, Line among others .The aesthetic appearance and features of a product are the most censorious elements for the accomplishment of a product .The production can be achieved by joining pieces of fabric wastes together to obtain the required length and width of the materials using patchwork , quilting sewing techniques , research/development and sustainable living.

Sustainable living is achieved by making choices that aim to reduce our individual and collective environmental impact by making positive changes to offset climate change and reduce environmental damage. In this work homemakers in cross river, can use fabric waste to produce household linen, this will impact positively on their living and will reduce blockage of drainage with liters of fabric waste, and the burning of fabric waste that pollute the air. This will help to improve on the effect of climate change.

Research and Development design is a process used to develop and validate educational products, (Gall, Gall & Borge, 2007). The steps of this process are usually referred to as R&D cycle which consist of studying research findings pertinent to the product to be developed, developing the product based on the finding, field testing it in settings where it will be used eventually, and revising it to correct any deficiency found. However, the researchers used research and development process with modification, to ease the process of designing product this research was limited to five steps.

Research Questions

1. What are the household clothing items that could be produced from fabric waste for sustainable living of Homemakers in Cross River.?
2. What is the acceptability level on the aesthetic attribute of the produced household clothing items from fabric waste in Cross River?

3. What is the acceptability level on the aesthetic attribute of the produced household linen from fabric waste in Cross River?

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The study adopted Research and Development (R&D) design. This followed specific steps to develop household clothing items using fabric waste. These steps were: identification of household clothing items that could be produced from fabric waste, collection of fabric waste from dressmakers' shops, designing, production of five prototype household clothing items from fabric waste and testing the acceptability of the aesthetics attribute.

Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Cross River State. The state operates clothing construction business by dressmakers. Dressmakers generate much fabric wastes in the process of clothing construction which necessitates this research.

Population for the Study

The population for the study consists of all dress makers in Cross River State, making up four thousand, seven hundred and forty-seven (4,747) households, 7 Home Economics Teachers and 5 Home Economics/Clothing and Textile lecturer and 22 dressmakers.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size for this study was 344 respondents. This was determined using Taro Yamane formula $n = \frac{N}{1+N} (e)^2$ to get 310 homemakers, all twenty-two (22) Dressmakers, seven (7) Home Economics teachers and five (5) clothing lecturers were used for data collection. This is in line with Uzoagulu (2011), which stated that if the population is in a few hundreds, it is small and manageable all the number should be used. Also, 20 judges were drawn from the sample was used for the acceptability test.

Instrument for Data Collection

Two instruments used for data collection were, Household linen production from fabric Waste Questionnaire (HLPFWQ), and 9-point hedonic evaluation test Instrument. HLPFWQ was used to determine the household linen that could be produced from fabric waste. This instrument comprised of fifteen (15) items structured based on a four (4) point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. A 9-point hedonic scale evaluation test Instrument sought to assess the acceptability on the aesthetic attributes. The hedonic rating scale of 9 = like extremely, 8 = like very much, 7 = like moderately, 6 = like slightly, 5 = neither like no dislike, 4 = Dislike slightly, 3 = dislike moderately, 2 = dislike very much, 1 = dislike extremely were the response options.

The instruments were both validated and found suitable to respond to the objectives of the study. Data were collected in phases. In phases one, two research assistants were briefed by the researcher on how to administer and collect back the questionnaire, copies of questionnaire were handed to the respondents by hand, from the researcher with the help of the research assistants. The results were collected analyzed and the results were used in phase phases two.

Material and Tools for constructing Household Clothing Items

The materials needed for the production of household linen includes fabric wastes, measuring tape, scissors, Pencil, paper, Ruler, and eraser. Fabrics wastes were gathered, measured, designed, and cut out into different shapes and sizes; they were sewn together using machine stitches. Five household clothing items were developed. These include a quilted bed cover, curtain, tablecloth, throw pillow and Pillowcases, as seen in the flow chart below.

Flow Chart for Producing Household Linen

The flow chart Procedures explained how 5 prototypes of the houseline were produced from fabric waste. These household linens were displayed in the clothing and textiles laboratory of the department of Home Economics and Hospitality management in the faculty of vocational and technical education, University of Nigeria Nsukka. 20 judges accessed, based on aesthetics attributes, using the 9 point hedonic scale evaluation test instrument.

The Pictures of the Household Linen Produced from Fabrics waste

Quite bed Cover

Table Cover

Curtain

Throw Pillow

Pillow Cases

Method of Data Analysis: The data were analyzed using mean for research questions one, any item that has the mean value of 2.5 and above was accepted for the construction of Household linen from fabric waste. The mean scores of the judges were used to determine the acceptability level based on aesthetic attributes of the Household clothing items from fabric wastes. The mean values from 5 and above for the Hedonic rating scale were considered accepted.

Data presented in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation ratings of respondents on household linen produced from fabric waste in Cross River State. All the 15 items in the table had their means above the cut-off point of 2.50.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation ratings of Household linen that could be produced from Fabric waste N: 344

S/N	Household Linen	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Table Cover	3.82	0.54	A
2	Bed Cover	3.71	0.62	A
3	Curtain	3.58	0.79	A
4	Wall hanging	3.23	1.01	A
5	TV Cover	3.78	0.54	A
6	Head and Arm Rest	3.46	1.02	A
7	Place mat	3.32	0.92	A
8	Pillow Case	3.66	0.69	A
9	Throw pillow	3.57	0.61	A
10	Rag Rug	3.49	0.79	A
11	Shoe Hanger	2.77	1.02	A
12	Suit Hanger	2.96	0.96	A
13	House Coat	3.01	1.12	A
14	Chair pad	3.38	0.98	A
15	Glass Case	3.06	1.05	A
	Cluster Mean	3.39	0.41	A

Data on table 2 showed the items for testing the acceptability of household linen from fabric waste. The result revealed that all the items scored the mean between 7 and above the cut-off point of 5.00. The table also shows that the standard deviations (SD) of the items are within the range of 0.9-1.70 indicating that the mean values of the judges were close to each other in their rating.

Table 2: Mean rating of Judges on acceptability based on aesthetic attributes of household clothing items from fabric waste. N = 20

Item Statement	\bar{X}	S D
Arrangement of Shapes for Bed Cover	7.60	1.667
Arrangement of Shapes for Curtain	7.42	1.539
Arrangement of Shapes for Pillowcase	7.55	1.468
Arrangement of Shapes for Table Cover	7.68	1.293
Arrangement of Shapes for Throw Pillow	7.72	1.320
Texture for Bed Cover	7.84	1.214
Texture for Curtain	7.50	1.000
Texture for Pillowcase	7.75	1.020
Texture for Table Cover	7.40	1.273
Texture for Throw Pillow	7.80	1.056
Colour for Bed Cover	7.89	1.197
Colour for Curtain	7.70	1.418
Colour for Pillowcase	7.90	1.210
Colour for Table Cover	7.80	1.508
Colour for Throw Pillow	7.90	1.294
Rhythm for Bed Cover	7.63	1.300
Rhythm for Curtain	7.37	1.499
Rhythm for Pillowcase	7.68	1.416
Rhythm for Table Cover	7.58	1.121
Rhythm for Throw Pillow	7.74	1.240
Lines for Bed Cover	7.85	1.309
Lines for Curtain	7.60	1.603
Lines for Pillowcase	7.65	1.663
Lines for Table Cover	7.65	1.387
Lines for Throw Pillow	7.65	1.387
Balance for Bed Cover	7.90	.912
Balance for Curtain	7.75	.910
Balance for Pillowcase	7.45	1.356
Balance for Table Cover	7.85	1.089
Balance for Throw Pillow	7.75	1.293
General acceptability for Bed Cover	8.37	.597
General acceptability for Curtain	7.84	1.167
General acceptability for Pillowcase	7.95	.911
General acceptability Table Cover	7.84	1.834
General acceptability for Throw Pillow	8.16	.834

Discussion

The following household clothing items were shown to be produced from fabric waste, these include bedcover, table cover, curtain, wall hanging, TV cover, Head, and arm rest placement; pillowcase, Dusting cloth, Rag-Rug, Shoe Hanger, House coat, chair pad, glass case. Victor (2018) had listed most of the items produced from waste like those produced in this study. The researcher made use of fabric wastes from small scale dressmakers who includes, off-cut, end of rolls and scraps to produce household clothing items from fabric waste for home makers in Cross River State. Owodiong (2010) revealed that producing household clothing items from fabric wastes saves the

environment and generate income for householders. Dashita (2013) posited that fabric waste found in dressmakers' shops have the potentials for being used to produce useful materials.

Finding of the acceptability test on the aesthetics attributes of the produced household clothing items, on table 2 were all above the mean score of 5, indicating acceptability. Pongracz (2002) explained the waste management theory and provides an understanding that nothing is completely a waste and that the essence of human beings is to create something new and be creative. Veblen (1952) theory of adornment is concerned with decoration or making things attractive to improve appearance. This is supported by Ugwu (2018) who revealed that a positive attribute in consideration for producing household items from waste to beauty is how appealing and acceptable these items are to the consumers.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The production of household linen from fabric waste with such an esthetic value, will help in sustainability of homemakers both in housekeeping and in home decoration, without necessary buying expensive fabrics for such use. The use of fabric waste to produce household linen indicates that, nothing is completely a waste, in any waste there must be what you can do with, and that will be of benefit to you or the society. Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Dressmakers including tailors/seamstresses should utilize fabric pieces which are considered waste into household clothing items instead of burning them or throwing a large quantity of them into landfill or even littering them to cause health hazard, drainage blockage and environmental nuisance.
2. Home Economists can utilize the opportunity in training householders in the use of fabric waste as an opportunity to create wealth from waste.

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